

**AGENT-BASED
SUPPORT TOOL FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT
OF AGRICULTURE POLICIES**

D9.5 AGRICORE project website

Deliverable Number	D9.5
Lead Beneficiary	IDENER, AXIA
Work package	WP9
Delivery Date	M04
Dissemination Level	Public

www.agricore-project.eu

The Agricore project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 816078

Document Information

Project title	Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies
Project acronym	AGRICORE
Project call	H2020-RUR-04-2018-2019
Grant number	816078
Project duration	1.09.2019-31.8.2023 (48 months)

Version History

Version	Description	Organisation	Date
0.1	Template initialisation	IDENER	05.12.2019
0.2	Initial content contributions	IDENER	10.12.2019
0.3	Extended details on websites generation	AXIA	15.12.2019
0.4	Inclusion of internal website details	IDENER	17.12.2019
1.0	Final version	IDENER	30.12.2019

Executive Summary

The present document is the deliverable "D9.5 - AGRICORE project website" of the AGRICORE project, funded through the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 816078, and presents the development of the project website.

This deliverable is generated according to task 9.3: Communication Activities contained in Work Package 9: Communication and Dissemination of AGRICORE. This task covers the development of, among other communication materials, the project's internal and external websites. The creation of both sites as well as the additional one generated for the AGRIMODELS cluster are described in this deliverable.

Overall, the purpose of this deliverable is to document the process followed for the implementation of the three sites, namely: <https://www.agricore-project.eu>, <https://www.agrimodels-cluster.eu> and the project internal website.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
CMS	Content Management System
DoS	Denial of Service
EEAB	External Experts Advisory Board
EU	European Union
REA	Research Executive Agency

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1 Introduction

Deliverable D9.5 - AGRICORE project website is part of the overall communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of the project. Being one of the main objectives of the AGRICORE project to proceed with targeted dissemination and communication of the project's results, the websites here presented offer a unique possibility for the project members to centralise the communication of the project advances. The development of the webpages reinforces the general communication and dissemination activities in the project and adds up to other communication channels as the social media accounts, the press releases and the project's newsletters.

2 Developed websites

Two sites were originally scheduled for their development, namely the project's external website and the internal one.

2.1 Agricore public website

2.1.1 Introduction

The AGRICORE website is one of the project's main dissemination tools. The project website presents the project's overview, including objectives, project partners, news-events, material for public use and the EU use cases of AGRICORE tool. The website follows the EU recommendations on usability and accessibility, and it includes the logo of the European Commission. The developed visual identity has been applied to the design of the official project website. The setup of the project website was a collaboration between IDENER (project coordinator) and AXIA Innovation. IDENER developed the structure of the website and prepared the contents, while AXIA developed all the graphical elements. The website is published at <https://agricore-project.eu> and is publicly accessible from the internet.

2.1.2 Implementation details

The AGRICORE project website includes all the relevant information about the project, its objectives, its work plan and impact, the consortium participants, a dedicated news section, and other interesting links, including the project's Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter profiles, and the coordination team contact information. The website shows the following characteristics:

- An attractive, modern and professional website design
- A homepage presenting the overall project idea
- Latest news from the project as well as news, publications and important links of other parallel R&D activities
- Forthcoming events
- Easy access to the project information and documents, including the details of the work packages, partners and deliverables.
- Links to the AGRICORE Social Media pages.

Throughout the project implementation, the website will become a major tool to present the project research outcomes to a wide audience. The website will be regularly updated and enriched with new content and updates. Visitors of the AGRICORE website have access to all information about the project, they can download the project's promotional material (events posters, brochures and banners), read press releases and the public deliverables, subscribe to the newsletter and contact the consortium. The partners section, which includes links to the consortium members' profiles, provides interesting and easily accessible information on the expertise and involvement of each partner in the project. The Documents section of the AGRICORE website includes public deliverables, dissemination material and publications aimed mainly to disseminate the information to research institutions and universities. Followingly, the sections of the AGRICORE website are presented.

2.1.2.1 Creation and Design of the website

The AGRICORE project website has been developed using Wordpress during the early project stage and launched at <https://agricore-project.eu/>. Additionally, the project web hosting info email “info@agricore-project.eu” was created to be further used for social network profiles creation – registration, newsletter campaign, etc.

As already mentioned, the website has been developed using Wordpress. Wordpress is a Content Management System (CMS) implemented in PHP that uses MySQL as the database engine to store the information. WordPress is used by more than 60 million websites including 33.6% of the top 10 million websites as of April 2019, which renders it as one of the most popular content management system (CMS) solutions in use. The website has been deployed inside the IDENER's cloud environment which offers automatic backup and frequent system upgrades. Indeed, the basic Wordpress installation has been complemented with a set of plugins that enhance the functionality of this CMS. This includes several elements as:

- A free template which has been updated and modified to better represents the project's corporate identity.
- Several plugins to protect the site against different attacks, including unsolicited comments, spam, access attacks, DoS attacks, malware inclusion, unauthorized file modification, etc. This includes firewall and security monitoring embedded in Wordpress, which protects the website in addition to IDENER's own cloud protection measures.
- Content plugins to ease the task of generating content for the site to the maintainers, including several ones for allowing the inclusion of richer and better formatted content.
- Plugins for linking the content of the social media accounts used within the project.
- A plugin and the corresponding services to properly track the website traffic, enabling an enhanced analysis of the website visitors.

2.1.2.2 Website sections

This part of the deliverable list and describe all the sections generated within the website, providing also captures of the actual published website.

2.1.2.2.1 Homepage

The homepage contains the project title as well as a brief summary of the project. The upper part of the screen shows a navigation panel, using a common structure. Homepage also displays EC logo and H2020 framework logo.

The AGRICORE project

The Aim

AGRICORE addresses the environmental and climatic impact assessment of policies by means of a dedicated module aimed to establish links between targeted policies and the corresponding impact KPIs on farmers' practice.

The Project

The AGRICORE project proposes a novel tool for improving the current capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture by taking advantage of the latest progress in modelling approaches and ICT.

The Model

The main objective of the AGRICORE project is to develop a new generation of ABM tool taking advantage of the latest progress in computational science and ICT.

Specific Objectives

To develop a European data-sources index tool.

To minimise the time and user efforts currently required for the parametrisation and calibration of ABM models.

To develop an evolved agent-based model with improved capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture.

To produce a behavioural model of farmers mimicking their decision-making rationale.

To develop a flexible and integrated simulation suite.

To compile, analyse and show the produced information in an optimal way.

To provide social, economic and environmental impact assessments of agricultural policies at farm, sector and global levels.

To effectively integrate stakeholders' knowledge and to cooperate with policymakers.

To build a basis for credibility of the policy modelling work.

To develop a highly modular and customisable tool to allow further improvements as needs arise.

Latest News

RUR-04-2018 funded projects meet with main stakeholders

On 26 September, representatives of AGRICORE BESTMAP and MIND STEP projects, all funded under the RUR-04-2018 topic of the H2020

[Read more.](#)

AGRICORE Kick-off Meeting 24-25 September 2019, Seville, Spain

The project officially launched on the 1st of September 2019 and the two-day Kick-off Meeting was held on the 24th-25th

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎅🎁

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

AGRICORE participated at the EU Conference on Modelling for Policy support that took place on the 26th -27th of November in Brussels, Belgium.

For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/eventic... #EUmodelling #AgnResearch_EU #H2020

AGRICORE Partners

Strategic

THE PROJECT

OBJECTIVES

WORK PACKAGES

IMPACT

PUBLIC DELIVERABLES

PUBLICATIONS

INTERMEDIATE RESULTS

THE PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION UNDER THE AGRI-REGULATORY INNOVATION AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER (AGRI-RIKT) PROGRAMME

Privacy Policy

CONTACT US

Table 1 The AGRICORE homepage

2.1.2.2.2 About AGRICORE

A more detailed description of the project is given along with information regarding the AGRICORE project's objectives, workplan and impacts.

2.1.2.2.2.1 The project

This section provides a summary of the project scope.

What's Agricore?

The AGRICORE project proposes a novel tool for improving the current capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture by taking advantage of the latest progress in modelling approaches and ICT. Specifically, the AGRICORE tool will be built as an agent-based approach where each farm is to be modelled as an autonomous decision-making entity which individually assesses its own context and makes decisions on the basis of its current situation and expectations. This modelling approach will allow simulating the interaction between farms and their context (which will account for environment, rural integration, ecosystem services, land use and markets) at various geographic scales – from regional to global. To do so, advances in big data, artificial intelligence algorithms, mathematical solvers and cloud computing services will be applied to optimise the extremely-long parameterisation and calibration phase required by current agent-based tools, to better mimic the modelling of farmers' behaviour and interactions, to credibly assess the local effects of global events and EU policies, and in general to improve policy design, impact assessments and monitoring. The AGRICORE tool will be made as a highly modular and customisable suite, and it will be released as an **open-source** project so institutions can transparently update and improve the tool as needs arise.

Figure 1 The AGRICORE project

2.1.2.2.2.2 Objectives

A list of the project's objectives is summarised in this section.

The main objective of the AGRICORE project is to develop a **new generation of ABM tool** taking advantage of the **latest progress in computational science and ICT** (including advances in big data, artificial intelligence algorithms, mathematical solvers and cloud computing services) as a means to **overcome the challenges** that are still hampering their capacity for improving new policies design and for performing the related socio-economic and environmental assessments at various geographic scales – from regional to global.

This main goal can be further split in the next list of specific objectives:

1. **To develop a European data-sources index tool.** The partners will perform a comprehensive survey which will include EU statistics datasets, geo-reference databases, national and regional information sources and previous research results for the modelling of land use, policy, biophysical, social, economic and environmental aspects related to farming activities. The partners will identify synergies and analyse the integration of such information into the tools in AGRICORE.
2. **To minimise the time and user efforts currently required for the parameterisation and calibration of ABM models.** The partners will develop a state-of-the-art combination of big data extraction and fusion followed by a combinatorial optimisation step to construct synthetic populations mimicking the distribution and characteristics of the real populations of interest.
3. **To develop an evolved agent-based model with improved capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture.** The partners will elaborate on a dynamic quadratic model explicitly accounting for agent interactions and which computation is to be enabled by recent advancements in the capacities of mathematical solvers and ICT. This model structure will be a step ahead with respect to current ABM models to address main policy modelling challenges of today.
4. **To produce a behavioural model of farmers mimicking their decision-making rationale.** The partners will collect direct feedback from target groups through participatory research involving farm representatives and associations. This will improve the understanding of factors acting on farmers and their possible responses to these factors. This work will imply the identification of key drivers and parameters likely to influence farmer decision-making and understanding how policies could lead to the implementation of different options by farmers. Thanks to the collected information and complementary data extracted from the multiple databases considered, a behavioural model will be developed by means of the application of artificial intelligence algorithms.
5. **To develop a flexible and integrated simulation suite.** The partners will integrate all the modules composing the AGRICORE suite as a simulation environment ready for its use either for normative or positive purposes and which will have both ex-ante (for policy design) and ex-post (for monitoring) analysis capacity. Such an integrated suite will allow its connection with biophysical models and a large set of databases including multiple data sources and geo-referenced datasets (interoperability).
6. **To compile, analyse and show the produced information in an optimal way.** The potential amount of information that influences the development of a policy at local, sectorial and global levels is huge. The proper visualisation of such an amount of information is challenging, and it is key to ensure an adequate decision-making process. Accordingly, the partners will rely on big data analysis and big data-oriented visualisation tools and libraries (such as visualisation maps and results from previous EU research projects on interactive visualisation charts and plots).
7. **To provide social, economic and environmental impact assessments of agricultural policies at farm, sector and global levels.** The partners will design the AGRICORE suite to support the process of monitoring and assessing the impact of policies at farm, sector and global levels. Some of the impacts at farm level will be related to farm structure, production costs and land balance while at sector and global levels will include environmental and socio-economic factors. In addition, impacts will be assessed for the whole rural area with an emphasis on environment, development and jobs.
8. **To effectively integrate stakeholders' knowledge and to cooperate with policymakers.** The partners will cooperate with main stakeholders' groups (including policymakers, researchers, data analysts and farmers) and will gather their needs and requirements in order to guide and enrich the AGRICORE design.
9. **To build a basis for credibility of the policy modelling work.** The partners will apply the AGRICORE suite to the ex-post (2014-2017) and ex-ante (2018-2020) policy assessment of three use cases (UC1, UC2 and UC3), which have been selected to test the tool at various geographic scales (UC1 corresponds to the regional level while UC2 and UC3 aims to the national level) and for different policy instruments (UC1 policy instrument relates to environmental impacts, UC2 relates to the delivery of ecosystem services and UC3 relates to the socioeconomic aspects of the integration of agriculture in rural society). The results to be obtained will offer opportunities to publish in good level journals to keep researchers and policymakers at their institutions sufficiently motivated and to build a basis for credibility of the policy modelling work.
10. **To develop a highly modular and customisable tool to allow further improvements as needs arise.** The AGRICORE suite will be implemented as a highly modular IT architecture composed of interchangeable and expandable modules so other researchers can contribute to its development as well. To facilitate this, AGRICORE will be released as an open-source project to be abundantly documented, communicated and disseminated (indeed, almost all deliverables will be made public). Additionally, the partners plan a set of dedicated actions towards clustering, coordination with policymakers and transfer of project's results.

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP
The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🇪🇺

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

AGRICORE participated at the EU Conference on Modelling for Policy support that took place on the 26th-27th of November in Brussels, Belgium.

For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/policyevents/ #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #EU2020

Dec 2, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

Take a look at the 1st AGRICORE Press Release! #EU_H2020

Oct 21, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

Kick-off Meeting of the #AGRICORE H2020 Project was held on 26th-28th September, 2019 at Aemopolis Business Centre in Seville, Spain hosted at the premises of the coordinator @IDENER. #EU_H2020

Oct 18, 2019

Load more Tweets

Embed View on Twitter

Table 2 The AGRICORE Objectives

2.1.2.2.2.3 Workplan

A list of the work packages within the AGRICORE project is given in this section

The screenshot shows the 'Work Packages' section of the AGRICORE project website. It lists 11 work packages (WP1-WP11) with their respective IDs (MI-31 to MI-48). Each package has a 'Read the WP' button. To the right, there are tweets from @AgricoreP, including a Christmas message and a tweet about a meeting in Seville. A 'Work Package Gantt' chart is also visible at the bottom right.

Table 3 Work Packages Section

2.1.2.2.2.4 Impact

The impact of the AGRICORE project is presented in this section

+ In the short term

- In the medium to long term

• Improvement of policy design:

- **Positive purpose:** The AGRICORE tool is tailored to be used for a positive purpose, that is, for representing or imitating the real system in response to a given policy as closely as possible.
- **Normative purpose:** As an alternative, the AGRICORE tool can also be configured to account for a normative purpose, that is, to automatically choose the best parameters defining a policy scheme in terms of a certain objective function (for instance, to automatically choose the optimal value of a price support policy to maximise the survival of SMEs under a given market context). To do so, the "positive" configuration of the agent-based simulation module will be completed by an additional optimisation layer accounting for the policy instrument optimisation.
- **Ex-ante analysis:** AGRICORE will allow to run ex-ante evaluations of different policy schemes with heterogeneous populations of farmers. To do so, the user (for instance, a policy maker) would define the population of interest along with the specific policy to be evaluated and a corresponding context. Then, the AGRICORE tool would simulate the evolution of the farmers composing the population as the response to the given policy. This, along with the corresponding impact assessments, will allow the user to have an informed decision on which policy schemes are best to be promoted.

• Monitoring:

- **Ex-post analysis:** Additionally, the AGRICORE tool can be used for the monitoring of a given policy during the time period in which the policy is implemented. Indeed, the receding horizon strategy executed in AGRICORE allows to, every time step, integrate real feedback of the policy performance. Such feedback would be incorporated in the first stage of the optimisation process implemented by AGRICORE, so the state of the population is updated accordingly. On the one hand, this will allow comparing the expected status of the population with its actual status (along with the expected and actual impacts). On the other hand, this will allow refining the assessment of the impacts of the policy in subsequent time steps considering the real feedback collected in the current time step (for instance, in a mid-term policy evaluation).

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎅🎁

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

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For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/ventic... #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #H2020

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

Take a look at the 1st #AGRICORE Press Release! #EU_H2020

Figure 2 Impact Section

2.1.2.2.3 Consortium details

2.1.2.2.3.1 Project Coordinator

Project Coordinator

IDENER is a private research SME company composed of a team of researchers with a sound scientific background in disciplines comprising the branch of systems engineering, such as electronics and computer, systems integration and control, and process engineering.

The company, located in Aerópolis Science and Technology Park (Seville, Spain), was founded in 2010 by a group of PhD holding engineers. From that time forward, IDENER has positioned as a valued partner of top European Research centres, Universities and technology firms.

Mr. Carlos Leyva Guerrero

Mr. Carlos Leyva Guerrero, MSc in Telecommunications Eng. in 2011 at the University of Seville (Spain), is specialised in software and hardware engineering and joined IDENER in 2010. He is in charge of the IT and Industry 4.0 Applications department where he leads the software implementation done in the related projects. His works are indeed focused on systems integration and processes scale-up as well as in the implementation and deployment of laboratory developed solutions in industrial environments.

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎅

Dec 20, 2019

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For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/info/en/eventic... #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #H2020

Figure 3 Coordinator section

2.1.2.2.3.2 Management details

Management

- + **Project coordinator (PC): Mr. Carlos Leyva Guerrero**
- + **General Assembly (GA)**
- + **Executive Management Board (EMB)**
- + **Exploitation and Dissemination Team (EDT)**
- **External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)**

The EEAB will be composed of up to six independent international experts. Given the scope of the project, the goal will be to include members from relevant organisations, including the IPTS JRC, the DG-AGRI, the OECD and FAO as well as other researchers in the agricultural policy impact assessment area. The establishment of the EEAB will be initiated during the project kick-off meeting. Due to the previous relation and collaboration of project partners with the targeted organisations, it is expected that the EEAB will be formalised within the first 6 months of the project. The members will be contacted frequently and invited to assist to project meetings, so they can provide inputs regarding the project development.

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎅

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

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Figure 4 Management details

2.1.2.2.3.3 Partners

Detailed information is given regarding the consortium partners. The logos of the partners and a link to their respective websites are available, as well as a description of their role in the project.

Figure 5 Partners Section

2.1.2.2.4 EU Use cases

Description of the three use cases covered within the project.

Greece – Socio-economic impacts (AUTH)

Current situation

Greece has 5 less developed, 6 transitional and 1 more developed regions under article 2014/99/EU definitions. In addition, the country is one of the member states eligible for funding from the Cohesion Fund pursuant to Article 4. It has a population of 10.75 million people and covers an area of 131,957 km². The region includes four level 1 NUTS areas, EL3, EL4, EL5 and EL6 (considering the last changes in NUTS). Agriculture in Greece is one of the main employers, with around 1,212,720 people working in it. The agricultural sector in the country contrasts with the rest of Europe, having much smaller farms on average. The country accounts for 723,101 agricultural holdings and a total cultivated area of 3,477,930 ha, resulting in an average area per holding of 4.8 ha. Indeed, 89% of the total number of farms are smaller than 10 ha. In general, in 2014, there was a low penetration of young farmers in the sector, with only 7% of the holdings owned by young people, while 35% was owned by people over 65 years. This highlights the old-aged workforce and the need for its renewal.

The selected instrument is the "M6.1: Start-up aid for young farmers" sub-measure, which is included in the national programme for the period 2014-2020. It is derived from Article 19 of the 1305/2013 EAFRD regulation. The aim of this instrument is the establishment of farmers-entrepreneurs and the increase of agricultural holdings' competitiveness through age-based and higher-skilled renewal. The measure contemplates providing a lump sum to holdings producing between 8,000 and 100,000 €/year and managed by new young (<40) farmers. It covers up to 100% of the development of new business plans (between 17,000 and 22,000 per farm).

Improvement potential

This use case will analyse the M6.1 measure impact on Greece, focusing on the socio-economic aspects. The ex-post analysis will be done for the period 2014-2017 and the ex-ante impact analysis will be done for the period 2018-2020. To that end, AGRICORE will use several data sources including FADN, FSS, the Hellenic Statistical Authority, the different Chamber of Commerce and MinAgric. This information will be complemented with information provided by the national and regional governments and with participatory research conducted among the different stakeholders involved in the use case. Biophysical models (generic and crop-specific) will be used to calculate the productivity and the yield of the exploitations on different climate scenarios.

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP
The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎁

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP
AGRICORE participated at the EU Conference on Modelling for Policy support that took place on the 26th -27th of November in Brussels, Belgium.
For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/polen/evencio... #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #H2020

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP
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For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/polen/evencio... #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #H2020

Table 4 EU Use cases section

2.1.2.2.5 Outputs

Every visitor of the website has access to the project’s public documents regarding dissemination activities and official results.

In the AGRICORE project, 59 out of 71 deliverables have been classified as public to ensure the transferability of the information generated during the project.

Public deliverables will be posted here in the near future.

Tweets by @AgricoreP

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

The #Agricore team wishes Merry Christmas and a wonderful New Year! 🎄🎁

Dec 20, 2019

AGRICORE Project @AgricoreP

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For more information visit: ec.europa.eu/polen/evencio... #EUmodelling #AgriResearch_EU #H2020

Figure 6 Publications Section

2.1.2.2.6 News

News regarding the project are uploaded to this section. This section will be constantly updated during the project

Figure 7 News Section

2.1.2.2.7 Contact

A contact form for communication with the coordination team as well as contact details are given in this page

Figure 8 Contact Section

2.2 Agricore internal website

2.2.1 Introduction

The development of an internal way to share knowledge is a requirement for those projects aiming to enable true multidisciplinary teamwork. In the AGRICORE project, data scientists, IT experts, agriculture experts and modellers and policy experts collaborate together to improve the current policy impact assessment capabilities in Europe. To enable this advanced collaboration between partners, the consortium decided to adopt the Confluence software as the main tool for their collaboration. Confluence is a collaboration software developed by Atlassian that enhances the knowledge sharing between different actors. Specifically, the software has advanced capabilities for real-time simultaneous edition of documents, while keeping track of the individual modifications done. The system also enables searches across the whole project material, which is quite useful for a multidisciplinary collaboration project.

2.2.2 Implementation details

The Confluence software has been deployed inside of IDENER's cloud infrastructure. A license for the whole team was purchased by IDENER and linked to the deployed software. The portal has been configured to ensure secure access to it and producing iterative backups to block any potential content loss. The Confluence software offers a Wiki-like interface for generating content, where web pages are nested to develop a project categorisation. Specifically, the next sections have been created:

- Project Handbook

This section covers the details about the procedures to be followed inside the consortium towards a proper execution of the project. Specifically, the content of this section is the same as the D10.1 - Project management Handbook (Confidential), submitted within the first month of the project schedule. This includes procedures for preparing, reviewing and submitting the deliverables, the arrangement of technical and bi-weekly meetings, the procedures to establish the EEAB, etc.

- Contact List

This section contains the details of all the contributors of the project, linking them to the specific project section they are working on.

- Meeting notes

This section entails the detailed meeting minutes for every event arranged or attended by the AGRICORE partners, including and focusing on the internal bi-weekly meeting and the general assembly ones. It offers a centralised point for reviewing discussed topics and enables the assignment of tasks to individuals within the project.

- Deliverables

This section contains all the data associated with the project deliverables. Each deliverable has its own page where the partners include their contributions. The system offers the automatic initialisation (using a basic template) of the deliverable, including the main sections to be added. Later, the deliverable responsible can define its main sections and the people that should contribute to them. It also supports the online reviewing of the deliverables allowing the insertion of comments on the documents. Lastly, it offers a system for exporting the generated content. This process is further detailed in Deliverable D9.4 - Corporate Identity, which is also public.

- Use cases

This section contains all the data related to the Use cases of the project. One sub-section is available for each one, aiming to offer a unique entry-point for all the work strictly related to each use case.

- WP Subsections:

In addition, each WP has its own subsection where the material tied to a specific WP is included. This also entails detailed subsections for non-technical WPs as WP8 - Exploitation, clustering and open sourcing, WP9 - Communication and dissemination, WP10 - Project Management and WP11 - Ethics requirements.

- File lists:

This section provides easy access to all the files uploaded into the portal.

As the Confluence site is available and used only by project partners, no further detail is included in this section. Nonetheless, if any other H2020 project participant or coordinator is interested in knowing how the Confluence software can be used to boost the collaboration within H2020 projects, they can contact the project consortium through the contact section of the public website. Indeed, the methodology used in this project for collaborating through Confluence is founded in previous experiences in other H2020 projects where the use of this software has contributed to the successful execution and management of the project.

2.3 AGRIMODELS cluster website

2.3.1 Introduction

In addition to the two initially planned websites (public and internal AGRICORE websites), both IDENER and AXIA have collaborated on the implementation of a third website. The AGRICORE project has been funded within the RUR-04-2018 topic of the H2020 program. At the same time, another two projects (BESTMAP and MIND STEP) were founded on the same call. Following the AGRICORE collaboration plan and also the suggestions of both the REA and DG-AGRI, the three projects have joined efforts to set up a cluster for enhancing the collaboration between them. This cluster has got the name of AGRIMODELS cluster and a webpage have been developed to centralise the public dissemination information for the three projects. This does intentionally overlap with the three individual dissemination strategies of the projects, aiming to increase the overall visibility of all of them and allowing easy access of any reader to the other projects funded in the same topic.

2.3.2 Implementation details

The AGRIMODELS cluster website has been developed following the same methodology as the one mentioned for the AGRICORE project. Indeed, a Wordpress site has been developed in collaboration between IDENER and AXIA following the same technical implementation details (security, plugins, etc). The cluster website is published at <https://agrimodels-cluster.eu> and is composed of only one section, the homepage.

The homepage has been designed considering the simplicity as the main goal. Indeed, the main objectives of this site are two:

- Provide a unique access point for the cluster and the three projects funded under the RUR-04-2018 topic.
- Offer a calendar with all the events related to the areas covered by the topic, namely agriculture model developing, impact assessment and policy modelling in Europe.

Following these objectives, the next captures detail the current status of the website. In early 2020, the Communication and Dissemination experts of the three projects will meet and will develop a procedure for including the required events in the calendar sections.

Agrimodels Cluster

Background

On 31 October 2017, the European Commission opened a call for projects (RUR-04-2018) aiming to improve the modelling capabilities for agriculture which would ultimately support evidence-based policymaking in the sector. The specific request from the EC was:

Society assigns an increasing number of objectives to the policies influencing the agricultural sector and rural areas that it expects to see fulfilled. Therefore, justifications for policies extend well beyond mere food production. Evidence-based policy making implies the development and maintenance of appropriate instruments for use in the design of these policies and for the monitoring of their effects, taking advantage of new socio-economic approaches and increased possibilities opened up by progress in the ICT area.

Modelling policies dealing with agriculture and the related management of renewable resources at various geographic scales implies the development of a new architecture taking advantage of progress in modelling approaches and ICT. Given the focus on local effects of global events and EU policies, new approaches should take into account the individual decision-making unit (e.g. agent-based or machine learning-based approaches). Modelling will include such aspects as the environmental and climatic impacts of farming, delivery of ecosystem services modelling of aspects ranging from product / sector to farming systems, structural change including the transfer of production factors such as land, the integration of agriculture in rural society and will allow the establishment of links with biophysical models and geo-referenced datasets. Proposals will develop modelling at various geographic scales – from regional to global. They will build a highly modular and customisable suite of tools which will allow flexible use and further improvements as needs arise.

The projects

As a response to this call, three projects proposed innovative approaches to increase modelling capabilities in the agriculture sector. These projects have coordinated together forming the AGRIMODELS cluster in order to coordinate the potential synergies between them. Please find below the description for each one of them.

Events

November 2019

[SUPREMA] Training on CAPRI
 November 5, 2019 - November 8, 2019
<https://www.suprema-project.eu/training-sessions/capri-training>
 See more details

EU Conference on modelling for policy support
 November 26, 2019 - November 27, 2019
<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/event/conference/eu-conference-modelling-policy-support>
 See more details

The three projects participating in this closure have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreements No 816078, 817501 & 817566.

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Table 5 AGRIMODELS cluster website

AGRICORE	BESTMAP	MIND STEP
<p>The AGRICORE project proposes a novel tool for improving the current capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture by taking advantage of the latest progress in modelling approaches and ICT.</p> <p>Website Contact</p>	<p>BESTMAP will develop a new modelling framework using insights from behavioural theory, linking existing economic modelling with individual-farm Agent-Based Models.</p> <p>Website Contact</p>	<p>Making use of improved possibilities opened up by progress in the ICT area, MIND STEP will improve the exploitation of available agricultural and biophysical data and will include the individual decision making (IDM) unit in policy models.</p> <p>Website Contact</p>

Table 6 Project details

3 Conclusions

This deliverable contains all the information related to the development of AGRICORE project websites (public and private) as well as of the AGRIMODELS cluster one. With the on-time publication of these webpages, the consortium provides an easy way for external stakeholders to get an idea of the work being done in the AGRICORE project (and in the others participating in the cluster) as well as an easy way to contact the right persons within those consortiums.

For preparing this report, the following deliverables have been taken into consideration:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due date
D9.4	AGRICORE corporate identity	AXIA Innovation	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	4
D9.5	AGRICORE project website	IDENER	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	4